

Determinants of Deposit Mobilization in Commercial Banks of Ethiopia.

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Received: Sep 27, 2025

Accepted: Oct 27, 2025

Published: Nov 13, 2025

Abstract

Deposits are the lifeblood of the banking Industry; Hence, deposit mobilization is critical to Banks, a fundamental part of banking activity. (Banson, et al, 2012), the study focused only on one of the areas of finance, which involves determining Commercial banks' deposits. This paper empirically examines the determinants of Deposit mobilization in commercial banks of Ethiopia for the period 2015-2024. From the total of Eighteen Banks in Ethiopia that were engaged in commercial banking activities, eight commercial banks were selected as a Sample based on the year of establishment, the Capacity of all Key Performance Indicators, and the availability of data. To arrive at the generalized idea, the researcher used these Selection Criteria to achieve the maximum number of observations through a purposive sampling technique. The sampled commercial Banks were Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, Awash International Bank S.C., Dashen Bank S.C., Bank of Abyssinia S.C, United Bank S.C., Cooperative Bank of Oromia, Wegagen Bank S.C, and Nib International Bank S.C. The researcher used secondary data as a source, which were gathered from the annual reports of eight commercial banks. The specific data were collected from financial statements Bank records, journals, websites, and relevant literature. The researcher employed quantitative research methodology and techniques using an econometric model and Descriptive Analysis in order to address the research questions. Multiple regression using OLS (Ordinary Least Square) estimates of the dependent (Total Deposit growth) and four independent external variables, Inflation, Deposit interest rate, Broad Money Supply, Growth per capita, and two internal factors, return on equity and loan to deposit ratio, were employed. Different diagnostic tests (test for assumption of Heteroscedasticity using estatstest, specification error using linktest, multicollinearity using correlation matrix) were conducted to check the appropriateness of the model. The results reveal that deposit interest rate and growth per capita are positively and statistically significant on bank deposit growth; whereas, inflation rate, return on equity, broad money supply and loan to deposit ratio influence is negatively and statistically significant on bank deposit growth. The research recommends that the Government should decrease the supply of broad money to the economy, devise a mechanism to control inflation, increase deposit interest rate and give more attention to investment and commercial banks loan to loan-to-deposit ratio to be kept minimum.

Keywords: Commercial Banks, Deposit Mobilization, Determinants, Ethiopia, Bank deposits.

1. Introduction

Deposit Mobilization is one of the primary functions of a Commercial bank. Deposits mobilized by banks play a key role not only as an important source of funds for banks but also as a n instrument for promoting saving and banking habit among the people. Deposits are essential raw material for the banking industry, mainly as a source of working fund.

Commercial banks are expected to make efforts in both the rural and urban areas for mobilizing savings in the form of their deposits which are beneficial to them and the country as well. Ketema (2017)

The success of the banking greatly lies on the deposit mobilization. Performances of the bank depend on deposits, as the deposits are normally considered as a cost-effective source of working fund. Mobilization savings helps to expand banking operations. Commercial Banks must tap deposits from both urban and rural areas. This helps the banks to provide large amount of funds to priority sectors for development. (Shettar, 2014)

The successful functioning of commercial banks depends on the extent of funds mobilized. Deposits are the life blood of banking companies. Deposits constitute a vital source of funds required for banking business.

2. Statement of the Problem

Deposit is the most liquid money that is found in the treasury of the bank and which is ready to be borrowed by a body in need of the fund. A deposit of the bank may be affected by different factors. One of the problems in mobilizing deposit is that banking activities in developing countries are limited to the officially existing marketing activities and the people in the countries have not been Commercial banks play a crucial role in mobilizing savings from the public and channeling them into productive investments that support economic growth and development. In Ethiopia, deposit mobilization is particularly significant as banks are the primary sources of finance due to the underdeveloped capital market. Despite its importance, the performance of commercial banks in mobilizing deposits has been inconsistent and often below the potential of the economy.

Several challenges continue to constrain deposit mobilization in Ethiopia. Rapid inflation erodes the real value of savings, discouraging households from keeping money in banks. Deposit interest rates have often been unattractive, reducing incentives for savers compared to alternative investments such as real estate, foreign currency holdings, or commodities like gold. Furthermore, limited branch networks in rural areas, low levels of financial literacy, inadequate banking technology, and weak customer service have further hindered the ability of banks to attract deposits.

In addition, institutional and policy-related factors such as regulatory restrictions, limited financial inclusion initiatives, and lack of public trust in the banking system pose further challenges. While some studies have examined aspects of banking performance in Ethiopia, there is limited comprehensive research that systematically investigates the combined effect of economic, bank-specific, and institutional factors on deposit mobilization.

This knowledge gap makes it difficult for policymakers, regulators, and bank managers to design effective strategies to strengthen deposit mobilization and enhance the banking sector's role in economic development. Therefore, it is essential to empirically investigate the determinants of deposit mobilization in commercial banks of Ethiopia to identify the most critical factors influencing savings behavior and to propose policy and managerial recommendations.

The research findings indicate that there is inconsistency in the result. The number of studies conducted in selected variables were also limited including number of selected Commercial banks. This research aims to fill the observed gap by including the return on equity, which has not been previously researched, and by identifying and analyzing the determinants of deposit mobilization in commercial banks in Ethiopia.

3. Rationale and need of the Study

The study conducted on the Determinants of Commercial Banks' deposit mobilization is expected to be used by all stakeholders. Accordingly, the following are the significances that are attained from the study:

- ✓ This study is helpful to Commercial banks to manage their deposit by identifying factors

determining deposit mobilization and further identifying which variable is the most important so that more emphasis can be given

- ✓ It provides information to minimize the impact of factors determining deposits mobilization by enabling them to design effective strategies.
- ✓ It serves as a source of reference for further studies in the area of deposit mobilization.
- ✓ Identifying the determinants of deposit mobilization is critical for formulating policies that enhance banking performance and financial inclusion.
- ✓ This study seeks to fill that gap by identifying macroeconomic, bank-specific, and behavioral factors influencing deposit growth and formulating better deposit mobilization strategies.
- ✓ The National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) regulates interest rates and financial inclusion policies. This study provides evidence-based insights for policymakers to enhance deposit growth strategies.
- ✓ Moreover, with the increasing digitalization of banking services, understanding how technological advancements affect deposit mobilization is crucial for developing strategic banking solutions (National Bank of Ethiopia, 2022).

This study seeks also to fill existing literature gaps by analyzing both internal and external influences on deposit mobilization, offering practical recommendations for policymakers and bank manager

4. Review of Previous Studies and Gap Analysis

4.1 Review of Previous Studies

Deposit mobilization has been widely studied as it is one of the fundamental functions of commercial banks and a key determinant of financial intermediation and economic growth. Previous studies have focused on economic factors, bank-specific factors, and institutional factors that influence deposit levels.

International Studies

Globally, researchers such as Sharma (2011) and Olokoyo (2012) have emphasized that deposit interest rate, inflation, and income levels are primary determinants of savings mobilization in banks. Mishra (2010) highlighted that financial deepening, banking outreach, and customer confidence significantly affect deposit growth in developing economies. Similarly, in Kenya, Ngugi and Kabubo (2013) found that macroeconomic variables such as inflation and GDP growth play an important role in determining deposit levels, while bank-specific factors like service quality and branch expansion are also significant.

Ethiopian Context

In Ethiopia, several scholars have attempted to study deposit mobilization from different angles. Getaneh (2016) examined private commercial banks and found that inflation and deposit interest rate significantly influenced deposit growth. Dereje (2018) identified bank-specific factors such as branch expansion, service delivery, and customer awareness as crucial in mobilizing deposits. Hibret (2019), in a case study of the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, concluded that macroeconomic instability, low deposit rates, and limited financial inclusion are major constraints.

Tesfaye (2020) emphasized the role of financial literacy and customer trust in banking institutions, pointing out that lack of awareness remains a barrier for rural deposit mobilization. In addition, National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) reports highlight persistent gaps between deposit growth and credit demand, suggesting that weak deposit mobilization undermines banking sector development.

4.2 Gap Analysis

It was discussed on the literature part, most of the study undertaken are related to the topic of determinants of deposit mobilization in all or selected commercial banks using some internal and external factors of the industry. Different researchers in different research techniques and

different independent variables showed different effects on bank deposits.

- ✓ The inflation rate results positive effect by four researchers and a negative effect by three researchers who used as the independent variable.
- ✓ The deposit interest rate result showed a positive effect by eight researchers and a negative effect by one researcher.
- ✓ Return on equity ratio result not investigated by any of the researchers.
- ✓ Growth per capita GDP result showed positive effect and was researched by two researchers
- ✓ Broad money supply result showed positive result by three researchers and negative result by one researcher.
- ✓ Loan to Deposit ratio showed negative effect by four researchers and positive by one researcher this study seeks to fill this gap by comprehensively investigating the determinants of deposit mobilization in commercial banks of Ethiopia, using both macroeconomic indicators and bank-specific characteristics, and applying rigorous statistical analysis to provide evidence-based policy recommendations.

5. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

5.1 Theoretical Framework

5.1.1 Deposit Definition

The study on the determinants of deposit mobilization in commercial banks of Ethiopia is grounded in several key theories and models in economics and finance:

A. Financial Intermediation Theory

- ✓ This theory explains the role of banks as intermediaries between savers (depositors) and borrowers (investors). It suggests that efficient deposit mobilization depends on the ability of banks to build trust, reduce transaction costs, and provide attractive returns.
- ✓ Relevance: It provides the basis for analyzing how interest rates, bank efficiency, and accessibility affect deposit mobilization.

B. Keynes' Liquidity Preference Theory

- ✓ According to Keynes, people hold money for three motives: transaction, precautionary, and speculative. The decision to save in banks rather than holding cash is influenced by interest rates and expectations about inflation.
- ✓ Relevance: Helps explain the impact of interest rates and inflation on deposit levels in commercial banks.

C. Permanent Income and Life-Cycle Hypothesis (Friedman, Modigliani)

- ✓ These theories state that individuals' saving behavior depends on expected lifetime income rather than current income.
- ✓ Relevance: Explains how income levels, employment status, and economic stability influence deposit mobilization in banks.

D. Trust and Institutional Theory

- ✓ The public's willingness to deposit is influenced by trust in banking institutions, regulatory frameworks, and macroeconomic stability.
- ✓ Relevance: Helps explain how institutional credibility, governance, and financial regulations affect deposit mobilization

E. Banking Development and Financial Deepening Theory

- ✓ This theory emphasizes that financial development, expansion of bank branches, and accessibility of financial services enhance savings mobilization.
- ✓ Relevance: Provides a basis for analyzing how branch expansion, digital banking, and financial inclusion policies influence deposit growth.

5.1.2 Deposit mobilization

According to Thangam (2017) the saving and investment process in an economy is organized around a financial framework that facilitates economic growth. A well-designed financial

system promotes growth through effective mobilization of savings and their allocation to the most productive uses by either following a centralized approach or a decentralized approach or a combination of both. Typically, economies with underdeveloped capital markets adopt a centralized approach whereby financial intermediaries mobilize resources from savers and allocate them to borrowers. Traditionally, banks have played a curtail role in the financial intermediation process as they are able to deal more appropriately with transaction costs and information asymmetries in a financial system. As financial markets develop, transaction costs and information asymmetries reduce, the decentralized approach for guiding the saving-investment process also gains significance and households with surplus resources increasingly invest in capital market instruments. The empirical experience shows that virtually all the economies, including the market intermediated ones, banks have played a key role in resource mobilization, supporting the growth process, and the development of bank and other intermediaries, thereby facilitating the development of financial markets.

5.1.3 The Determinants of Commercial Banks' Deposits

The determinants of commercial banks' deposits are classified as macroeconomic factors and microeconomic factors that can affect the growth of commercial banks' deposits. These are discussed as follows: -

5.1.3.1 External determinants

The external determinants are variables that are not related to bank management but reflect the economic environment that affects the operation and deposit positions of Banks. The external factors that can affect a bank's deposit include factors such as; Deposit interest Rate, Inflation Rate, Growth per capita GDP, Broad money supply.

A) Inflation

According to Solomon et.al (2016) inflation is a major problem of most economies in the world, and it influences countries, both negatively and positively. Zou, et.al. (2011) stated that inflation is an important factor contributing to social and economic instability and disorder and is one of the main observed and tested economic variables both theoretically and empirically. It is one of the main problems of developing countries in the world. Inflation is the general increase in the level of prices of goods and services in an economy over some time. When the general price level changes, each unit of our currency value comes down and therefore buys less goods and services. The day to day increases in prices of commodities, especially of non-food items like oil and gas snatch money from savings of consumers and the uncertainty of prices for both food and non-food items, generate enthusiasm among people to earn more and more.

B) Deposit Interest rate

According to Dereje (2017) the main focus of every financial system is a financial intermediary that is, mobilizing financial resources from the surplus sector and lending to the deficit outlets to facilitate business transactions and economic development based on the monetary and fiscal policy of the nation. The attraction for getting the deposit from the surplus sector is interest payment, which must be reasonable and acceptable to the owner of the money.

According to Tafirei et.al (2014) Domestic savings comprise of public and private savings. To encourage private savings, the real interest rates should be positive. Furthermore, innovative saving schemes and investment bonds should be introduced to mobilize resources. Higher interest rates lead to increased savings and financial intermediation in improving the efficiency of savings and investment. The higher real interest rates increase the extent of financial intermediation, which in turn raises the rate of economic growth in developing countries.

C) Money Supply

According to Al-Qudah & Jaradat (2013, cited in kibebe 2016), Money supply is a measure of the total amount of money in an economy. Money supply (M2) is the summation of currency in circulation, demand deposit, time deposit and saving deposit. Money supply is the amount

of money within a specific economy available for purchasing goods or services.

The broad definition of money supply (M2+) is adopted which includes currency in circulation, demand deposits, quasi-money and foreign currency deposits.

The money creating activities of the deposit money banks impact directly on money supply and given that the central bank is responsible for controlling money supply in an economy, it is important to evaluate the role of these banking institutions on the convergence process. Excess money supply, whether created through the direct or indirect channels, influences economic activity (growth) and may provide downside risks on macroeconomic stability, impacting negatively on inflation, interest rates and exchange rate.

D) Per capita GDP

According to Jim (2008, cited in by Shemsu 2016), per capita is the level of GDP divided by the population of a country or region. Changes in real GDP per capita over time are often interpreted as a measure of changes in the average standard of living of a country. If households and firms desire to hold more money, deposits will increase. So, the relationship between income and deposits is positive that is as the income of the society increases, the same happens for the commercial bank's deposits.

5.1.3.2 Internal determinants

The bank-specific factors are factors that are related to internal efficiencies and managerial decisions. Such factors include determinants such as Return on equity and loan-to-deposit ratio.

A) Return on Equity

According to Tigest (2014) Return on equity is the return to shareholders on their equity. This means that, return on equity reflects the capability of a bank in utilizing its equity to generate profits. Relatively high or low ROE ratios will vary significantly from one industry group or sector to another. When used to evaluate one company to another similar company the comparison will be more meaningful.

Sustainable growth rates and dividend growth rates can be estimated using ROE assuming that the ratio is roughly in line or just above its peer group average. Although there may be some challenges, ROE can be a good starting place for developing future estimates of a stock's growth rate and the growth rate of its dividends. These two calculations are functions of each other and can be used to make an easier comparison between similar companies.

B) Loan-to-deposit ratio

The loan-to-deposit ratio (LDR) is used to assess a bank's liquidity by comparing a bank's total loans to its total deposits for the same period. The LDR is expressed as a percentage. If the ratio is too high, it means that the bank may not have enough liquidity to cover any unforeseen fund requirements. Conversely, if the ratio is too low, the bank may not be earning as much as it could be. Also, the LDR helps to show how well a bank is attracting and retaining customers. If a bank's deposits are increasing, new money and new clients are being on-boarded. As a result, the bank will likely have more money to lend, which should increase earnings. Although it's counterintuitive, loans are an asset for a bank since banks earn interest income from lending.

Deposits, on the other hand, are liabilities because banks must pay an interest rate on those deposits, albeit at a low rate.

5.2 Conceptual framework

From the above research gap the factors that determine the deposit of the bank is divided into two main parts those are the internal and external factors. This study used both internal and external determinants of bank deposit that are indicated as research gaps. The study has quantified how these variables are determining the deposit of all commercial banks. The conceptual framework of the relationship between the dependent variable (bank deposit) and independent variables (Inflation rate, Deposit interest rate, Return on equity, Growth per capita GDP, Broad money supply, and Loan to Loan Ratio).

6. Research Methodology

Introduction

According to Jembere (2014) a research design is the logic that links the data to be collected (and the conclusions to be drawn) to the initial questions of the study (Yin, 2003). If empirical research has no explicit research design, it has an implicit plan that guides the research process. For determining the case study design, five components need to be taken into account: the study's questions, its propositions, its unit of analysis, the logic linking the data to the propositions and the criteria for interpreting the findings (Yin, 2003).

6.1 Research Questions

General Research Question

- What are the major determinants that influence deposit mobilization in commercial banks of Ethiopia?

Specific Research Questions

- What is the effect of general inflation on commercial banks' deposits?
- How does the money supply affect commercial banks' deposits?
- What is the effect of the deposit interest rate on commercial banks' deposits?
- How does return on equity affect commercial banks' deposits?
- What is the effect of the loan-to-deposit ratio on commercial banks' deposits?
- How does growth per capita GDP affect commercial banks' deposits?

6.2 Research Hypothesis

Based on the Question, the study has tested the following hypotheses:

- H1** The average deposit interest rate has a significant positive effect on Commercial banks deposit in Ethiopia
- H2** Return on equity has a significant negative effect on Commercial banks deposit in Ethiopia.
- H3** The inflation rate has significant negative impact on Commercial banks Deposit in Ethiopia
- H4** The loan-to-deposit ratio has a significant positive effect on Commercial banks deposit in Ethiopia.
- H5** Growth per capita GDP has a positive and significant effect on Commercial banks deposit in Ethiopia
- H6** Broad money supply has a significant positive effect on Commercial banks deposit in Ethiopia

6.3 Research Design

The researcher investigated effects and relationships between deposit growth and its determinants, therefore, it is explanatory research Design, and the factors identified that affect the outcome have numeric value. This indicates that it is a quantitative approach.

Therefore, the researcher employed quantitative research methodology and techniques using an econometric model and Descriptive statistics Analysis in order to address the research questions. Multiple regression using OLS (Ordinary Least Square) estimates of the dependent (Total Deposit growth) and four independent external variables, Inflation, Deposit interest rate, Broad Money Supply, Growth per capita GDP and two internal factors, return on equity and loan to deposit ratio, were employed. It uses time series data covering the period from 2015 through 2024.

6.4 Sample and Population

There were eighteen commercial banks as at June 30, 2024. The Eighteen Commercial banks were treated as the population of the study. To arrive at the generalized idea, the researcher used the availability of data and the service years of Commercial banks to achieve the maximum number of observations through a purposive sampling technique.

Out of eighteen commercial banks that were registered and operated in Ethiopia, eight were selected. The sampled commercial Banks were Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, Awash International Bank S.C, Dashen Bank S.C, Bank of Abyssinia S.C, United Bank S.C,

Cooperative Bank of Oromia, Nib International Bank S.C, and Lion International Bank. The Criteria for Selection are mainly based on the Operation Period, Asset, Deposit, Profit, and Loan they have. Sampled Commercial Banks contribute more than 82% of total assets and profit, 76% of total loans granted, and 71% of total deposits of all commercial Banks of Ethiopia. Moreover, it covers above 68% of the total population. Except for the Development Bank of Ethiopia, because its mission is not that of a Commercial bank.

6.5 Method of Data Collection

The researcher used secondary data as the source. The researcher gathered data from annual audited financial Statement (i.e. Balance Sheet and Profit & Loss Statement) Report of Eight Sampled commercial banks, published reports from the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE), records, websites Research articles, books, journals related to banking and finance and Macroeconomic data (inflation, GDP, money supply) from Ethiopian Central Statistical Agency (CSA). The data were collected from 2015 to 2024 on annual base and the figures for the variables were on June 30th of each year under study.

6.6 Tools and tests of the Study

Tools of Research

In this research, the **regression analysis** was used to test if an independent variable influences a dependent variable and whether the effect is positive/negative and therefore, one dependent variable and six independent variables were regressed using econometric software **called STATA**

13. The dependent variable is deposit growth of commercial banks (DPG) and the six independent variables are inflation rate (INF), Deposit interest rate (DEPIR), Return on Equity (ROE), Growth per capita GDP(GPCGDP), Loan to deposit ratio (LDR), Broad money supply (BMS). The regression by ordinary least square method was done with the data of successive 10 years from the 2015 to 2024. This section presents the regression result of factors affecting the deposit in commercial banks in Ethiopia.

Tests of Research

Model Assumption Tests

This study focused on the relationship between deposit growth and the determinants of deposit mobilization. The researcher used econometric model of multiple regressions which contains one dependent variable, six independent variables, the constant term and the error term. The model chosen has taken the common classical regression model (CLRM) to analyze the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Accordingly, all the assumptions of the classical linear regression model have been checked. Heteroscedasticity was checked using Breusch-Pagan

/ Cook-Weisberg test to check the reliability, validity, and correctness of results.

Heteroscedasticity Test

It has been assumed that the variance of the errors is constant which is known as the assumption of homoscedasticity. If the errors do not have a constant variance, they are said to be Heteroscedasticity. There is no evidence for the presence of heteroscedasticity if the p-values are considerably in excess of 0.05.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of DPG, $\chi^2(1) = 0.22$, Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.6377$

Source: STATA 13 output

As shown above, the p-values is greater than 0.05, which indicates the absence of heteroscedasticity. Hence, it can be said that the variance of the error term is constant.

Specification Error Test

The specification error test is basically to check whether we need more variables in our model by running a new regression. We used linktest to test the model specification.

The thing to look for here is the significance of $_hatsq$ in the table below

Table 4. Link test

Source	Ss	Df	Ms	Number of obs=10		
Model	719.5793	2	359.78965	F(2,7)=395.58 Prob>F =0.0000		
Residual	6.36674049	7	.909534355	R-squared =0.9912 Adj R-squared =0.9887		
Total	725.94604	9	80.6606711	Root MSE = 0.9537		
DPG	Coef	Std.Err	T	P> t	[95%Conf.Interval]	
$_hat$.8733826	.2589681	3.37	0.012	.2610204	
$_hatsq$.0022865	.0046322	0.49	0.637	-.008667	
$_cons$	1.579975	3.343054	0.47	0.651	-6.325093	9.485042

Source: STATA 13 output

The p-value of $_hatsq$ is 0.637 and it is greater than 0.05. Hence it is not significant and implies that there is no specification error.

Multicollinearity Test

The test for multicollinearity was done by using correlation matrix. Correlation is a way to index the degree to which two or more variables are associated with or related to each other. Thus, the result of the test for the existence of multicollinearity between independent variables is presented in the test analysis using only independent variables as shown under on Table 5.

Table 5. Correlation Matrix

	DPG	INF	DEPIR	ROE	GPCGD P	BMS	LDR
DPG	1.0000						
INF	.0071	1.0000					
DEPIR	0.2267	-0.1964	1.0000				
ROE	-0.4132	-0.5592	0.3623	1.0000			
GPCGD P	-0.0610	0.4424	0.2484	-0.1793	1.0000		
BMS	0.3197	0.0381	0.3281	-0.3739	0.1882	1.0000	
LDR	-0.0514	0.2304	-0.1660	-0.6642	0.5373	0.2294	1.0000

Source: STATA 13 output

As to Lewis (1980), in order to find out the multicollinearity problem, the correlation among the independent variables should be less than 0.8, that is, the existence of a correlation of about 0.8 or more indicates a problem of multicollinearity. Thus, as shown on the correlation matrix on table 5 above, all the figures are below 0.8 which indicates that there is no problem of multicollinearity. Therefore, all the variables were retained for use in the estimations.

Descriptive Statistics

This section presents the descriptive statistics of dependent and explanatory variables used in this study. The dependent variable used in this study was deposit growth in private commercial banks and the explanatory variables were inflation (INF), Deposit Interest Rate (DEPIR), Return on Equity (ROE), Growth per capita GDP (PPCGDP), Broad Money Supply (BMS) and Loan deposit ratio (LDR). The descriptive statistics include mean, median, maximum, minimum, standard deviation and other statistical value. The result of the descriptive statistics and its interpretations are presented as follows.

Table 3. Summary of descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
DPG	10	25.766	8.981129	14.78	42.45
INF	10	15.06	11.44234	2.8	36.4
DEPIR	10	5.208	0.3732381	4.5	5.4
ROE	10	27.691	4.304627	23.52	34.14
GPCGDP	10	11.02	8.343434	0.9	32.2
BMS	10	27.04	5.454295	19.9	39.2
LDR	10	80.239	15.79942	54.54	96.73

Source: STATA 13 output

Model Specification

Model specification refers to the determination of which independent variables should be included in or excluded from a regression equation. In general, the **specification** of a regression **model** should be based primarily on theoretical considerations rather than empirical or methodological ones.

Model specification refers to the determination of which independent variables should be included in or excluded from a regression equation. In general, the specification of a regression model should be based primarily on theoretical considerations rather than empirical or methodological ones. A multiple regression model is, in fact, a theoretical statement about the causal relationship between one or more independent variables and a dependent variable. Indeed, it can be observed that regression analysis involves three distinct stages: the specification of a model, the estimation of the parameters of this model, and the interpretation of these parameters. Specification is the first and most critical of these stages. Our estimates of the parameters of a model and our interpretation of them depend on the correct specification of the model.

7. Analysis, Discussion and Interpretation

Introduction

This study aims to identify the determinants of deposit mobilization in Commercial banks in Ethiopia by taking the period from 2015-2024. Hence, this chapter presents the descriptive statistics and diagnostic test results of multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and also results of the regression analysis.

the regression analysis was used to test if an independent variable influences a dependent variable and whether the effect is positive/negative and therefore, one dependent variable and six independent variables were regressed using econometric software called STATA

13. The dependent variable is deposit growth of commercial banks (DPG) and the six

independent variables are inflation rate (INF), Deposit interest rate (DEPIR), Return on Equity (ROE), Growth per capita GDP(GPCGDP), Loan to deposit ratio (LDR), Broad money supply (BMS). The regression by ordinary least square method was done with the data of successive 10 years from the 2015 to 2024. This section presents the regression result of factors affecting the deposit in commercial banks in Ethiopia.

$$DPG = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * INF + \beta_2 * DEPIR + \beta_3 * ROE + \beta_4 * GPCGDP + \beta_5 * BMS + \beta_6 * LDR$$

Accordingly, Table 6 below presents the result of regression model that examines the effect of explanatory variables on deposit growth. Hence, DPG is dependent variable whereas inflation rate (INF), Deposit interest rate (DEPIR), Return on Equity (ROE), Growth per capita GDP(GPCGDP), Loan to deposit ratio (LDR), Broad money supply (BMS) are explanatory variables.

Table 6. Regression

Source	SS	Df	MS	Number of obs =10		
Model	719.357702	6	119.89295	F(6,3)=54.59 Prob>F =0.0037		
Residual	6.58833796	3	2.19611265	R-squared =0.9909 Adj R-squared =0.9728		
Total	725.94604	9	80.6606711	Root MSE = 1.4819		
DPG	Coef	Std.Err	T	P> t	[95%Conf.Interval]	
INF	-.9947211	.0848772	-11.72	0.001	-1.264838	-.724604
DEPIR	12.59466	1.782554	7.07	0.006	6.921781	
ROE	-5.12341	.3084676	-16.61	0.000	-6.105092	
GPCGDP	1.00295	.1178333	8.51	0.003	.6279517	
LDR	-.9589835	.0722301	-13.28	0.001	-1.188852	-.7291151
BMS	-.8402552	.1284675	-6.54	0.007	-1.249096	
cons	205.6417	16.57037	12.41	0.001	152.9074	258.376

Source: STATA 13 output

Based on the regression result, the relationship between the variables included in the model can, therefore, be represented as follows

$$DPG = 205.642 - 0.995 * INF + 12.595 * DEPIR - 5.123 * ROE + 1.003 * GPCGDP - 0.8403 * BMS - 0.959 * LDR$$

Interpretation of R-squared

R-squared tells how well the model containing the explanatory variables that were proposed actually explain variations in the dependent variable. Thus, table 4 shows R-squared coefficient of 0.9909 obtained from the estimated model revealing that 99.1 percent of variation in Deposit growth (DPG) is explained by the selected explanatory inflation rate (INF), Deposit interest rate (DEPIR), Return on Equity (ROE), Growth per capita GDP (GPCGDP), Loan to deposit ratio (LDR), Broad money supply (BMS).

The R-square result is valid because the researcher only included the above six variables of the bank specific, industry and macro factors.

Interpretation of Adjusted R-squared

In this research, Adjusted R² was inferred to see how much of the variables could be explained by the factors. From the table above the value of R² was found to be 0.9728 shows that approximately

97.28 percent of dependent variable is explained by the independent variables included in the model and the remaining 2.72% is unexplained. Thus, the result shows more satisfactory association of dependent and independent variables

Inflation Rate

As to Finger and Hesse (2009), inflation is the persistent increase in the general prices of goods and services within an economy over a given period. The inflation rate is the rate at which the price level increases. According to them, price can also determine commercial banks' deposit and it can be indicated by consumer price index. As shown on table 6, inflation rate has negative and significant impact on deposit growth. Inflation is supposed to have negative effect on deposit growth. This is because the increase in inflation will result a decrease in deposit growth. The coefficient of this relationship of -0.9947211 indicates that holding other things constant, a unit increase in inflation rate will lead to a 0.995 unit decrease in deposit growth but the relationship is statistically significant at 5% significance level.

Deposit Interest Rate

According to Helani et.al (2018) statement one of the most effective factors for deciding to deposit in banking system is the interest rate. Harald and Heiko (2013), also mentioned interest as one of the determining factors for commercial banks deposits. Philip (1968, in cited Helani et.al 2018), also states that the offering of attractive interest rate on bank deposits may be considered to have had a beneficial effect. Moreover, Mustafa and Sayera (2014) said that low deposit rates are discouraging saving mobilization. Bhatt (1970), said that the banking system is unlikely to be able to meet the demand for bank credit unless concerted policy is pursued to raise the rate of saving generally and the rate of saving in the form of deposits in particular. The deposit interest rate is paid by financial institutions to deposit account holders. Deposit accounts are attractive places to park cash for investors who want a safe vehicle for maintaining their principle, earning a small amount of fixed interest and taking advantage of insurance.

Return on Equity

ROE illustrates how much profit a company generates with the money shareholders have invested and how successful the firm's management team is at turning the cash put into the business into greater gains and growth for the company and investors. Companies cannot increase their earnings faster than they can boost their ROE without raising additional cash by taking on new debt or selling more shares

Growth per capita GDP

Changes in real GDP per capita over time are often interpreted as a measure of changes in the average standard of living of a country. If households and firms desire to hold more money, deposits will increase. So, the relationship between income and deposits is positive that is as the income of the society increases the same happens for the commercial bank' deposits.

Broad money supply

Mushtaq & Siddiqui (2016 cited in Nwe Ni Tun) mentioned two possible ways for the relation of money supply and deposit. If money supply increase, loanable funds may be cheaper, thus reducing cost of borrowing for corporate and individual customers. Therefore, consumption will be increased and reduce savings. Thus, money supply and deposits will have an inverse relationship. However, there may be argument that as more money is supplied to the economy, more deposits could put in banks accumulating the fund for transactional and investment purposes.

Loan to Deposit ratio

Loan to Deposit ratio is the ratio between the bank's total loans and total deposits. Loan to Deposit ratio is used to measure a banks' liquidity, which in turn influences the profitability of the banks. Total loan in the numerator is considered as investments or assets for a bank in the balance sheet. The total deposit in the denominator can be considered as debt since the individual depositors are essentially depositing money to the bank having an expected return equal to the prevailing deposit rates.

Result vs. Hypothesis

The finding in this study revealed that most of the variables' result is as per the hypothesized sign except for to deposit ratio and deposit interest rate. The hypothesized sign and effect against the result is discussed hereunder

H1; The average deposit interest rate has a significant positive effect on Commercial banks' deposits in Ethiopia

The researcher expected to get a positive correlation between deposit interest rate and deposit because the increase in deposit interest rate will increase deposit and thus, banks will need to increase more deposit interest rate which will lead to an increase in deposit. The result is consistent with the hypothesized sign the impact of deposit interest rate on deposit is found to be significant and therefore, the hypothesis formulated is accepted.

H2; Return on equity has negative effect on Commercial banks' deposits in Ethiopia

In this research, return on equity was expected to have negative and significant effect on deposit. This is because as return on equity increases, the deposit will decrease. Accordingly, the hypothesis formulated is accepted due to the significant effect of return on equity on deposit as per the hypothesis formulated.

H3: The Inflation rate has a negative and significant impact on Commercial banks' deposits in Ethiopia

Inflation was expected to have an inverse relationship with deposits. The result revealed that Inflation and deposit have negative relationship which is consistence to the hypothesis. The finding shows that increase in inflation will result decrease in commercial banks deposit. Accordingly, inflation has negative significant effect on deposit, the hypothesis formulated is accepted due to the negative correlation between inflation and deposit.

H4; loan to deposit ratio has a significant positive effect on Commercial banks deposit in Ethiopia.

A positive correlation was expected between loan to deposit ratio and deposit because more disbursement of loan is likely to attract depositors. The finding revealed that loan to depositors have negative correlation with deposit but the hypothesis formulated is rejected due to the negative significant impact of loan to deposit ratio on deposit

H5; Growth per capita GDP has positive and significant effect on Commercial banks deposit in Ethiopia.

The researcher expected that there is positive relationship between growth per capita GDP and deposit. This is because when growth per capita GDP increases, commercial banks can enjoy higher deposit. The result showed that growth per capita GDP has direct relationship with deposit which could be explained as when growth per capita GDP goes up, deposit also go up in same manner in commercial banks. Accordingly, the hypothesis formulated is accepted due to the positive relationship.

H6; Broad money supply significant positive effect on Commercial banks deposit in Ethiopia.

In this study, it was expected that there will be a positive relationship between broad money supply and deposit. This is because an increase money supply will result in an increase in deposit since banks have to mobilize more deposit. The finding is contrary with the hypothesized sign and it is found a negative effect and accordingly, the hypothesis formulated is rejected.

8. Significance of the study

The study conducted on the Determinants of Commercial Banks' deposit mobilization is expected to be used by all stakeholders. Accordingly, the following are the significances that are attained from the study:

Bank managers should focus on internal factors such as improving service quality, accessibility, Customer Service Excellency Acquiring, Provide Training programs should be introduced to improve financial literacy and build trust in the banking system and customer awareness programs.

- ✓ This study is helpful to Commercial banks to manage their deposit by identifying factors determining deposit mobilization and further identifying which variable is the most important so that more emphasis can be given
- ✓ The regulatory body can take as an additional input for future policy making.
- ✓ It provides information to minimize the impact of factors determining deposits mobilization by enabling them to design effective strategies.
- ✓ It serves as a source of reference for further studies in the area of deposit mobilization.
- ✓ Tax incentives on savings and financial inclusion programs may boost deposits.
- ✓ Policy makers should implement policies that stabilize inflation and interest rates to create a favorable banking environment.

Finding of the Study

In this Study, the Researcher Put the Following Finding for further Study.

- The determinants of commercial banks' deposits are classified as macroeconomic/ External/factors and microeconomic/Bank Specific/ factors that can affect the growth of commercial banks' deposits macroeconomic/External/ factors, including Deposit Interest Rate, inflation Rate, Growth Per Capita GDP and Broad Money Supply. (Alemayehu & Kibret, 2019) were as microeconomic/Bank Specific/ factors are Return on Equity/Profitability/and Loan to Deposit Ratio/ Liquidity.
- dependent variable average deposit growth of commercial banks and the independent variables; inflation rate, deposit interest rate, return on equity, loan to deposit ratio, Growth per capita GDP and broad money supply.
- regressed using STATA 13. Thus, the results from the regression analysis estimated by pooled panel regression model showed that deposit interest rate and growth per capita GDP have positive and significant effect on deposit growth whereas return on equity, inflation, loan to deposit ratio and broad money supply have negative and significant effect on deposit growth of Commercial banks. In this research, to loan-to-deposit ratio and Broad money supply was expected to have positive and significant effect on deposit growth but the study revealed that they have negative significant impact.
- GDP Growth, Exchange Rate & Economic Stability increases disposable income, leading to higher savings and deposits
- Challenges such as low savings culture, low public awareness of banking services, Low Trust, Financial literacy, informal financial systems and limited digital banking adoption hinder deposit growth.

Conclusion

The study tried to examine the determinants of deposit growth in Commercial banks in Ethiopia. Hence, on the basis of the major findings shown above, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Loan to deposit ratio has negative and statistically significant effect on deposit growth. This shows that the increase loan deposit ratio indicates that banks may not pay /allow depositors to withdraw their money, when banks fail to pay for its depositors then it faces liquidity risk that makes other depositors not to deposit in that particular bank.

The more liquid banks can attract the deposits. From the finding, it can be concluded that Loan

to deposit ratio decreases deposit growth.

Broad money supply has negative effect on deposit growth. An increase in money supply makes loanable funds cheaper, thus reducing cost of borrowing for corporate and individual customers. In this case, it is expected that people will increase consumption and reduce savings and thus money supply will have an inverse relationship with deposits growth. From the finding, it can be concluded that broad money supply decreases deposit growth.

Growth Per capita income has positive relationship with growth in deposit. That is, as the income of the individual increases the same happens for the commercial banks' deposits. When Income of individual increase the need for saving increase that in turn increase the deposit of Commercial banks deposit. Therefore, as an individual's per capita income increases the same will happen for Commercial banks deposits. Thus, it can be concluded that increase in individuals' per capita income will increase Commercial banks deposit. Therefore, banks can mobilize deposit in this situation.

Inflation was proved to have negative and statistically significant impact on deposit growth of Commercial banks in Ethiopia. This is because the increase in inflation will result in a decrease in asset money value. Individuals like to purchase stable materials such as land, building etc. than to put in banks. Therefore, it can be concluded that as inflation decrease growth of deposit in the banks.

Deposit interest rate was proved to have positive significant impact on deposit growth in Commercial banks of Ethiopia. The increase in deposit rate will attract individuals to put their money in banks. The need to increase deposit interest rate is to overcome the inflation which has negative impact on deposit rate. Therefore, it can be concluded that as deposit rate increase growth in deposit increase in Commercial banks of Ethiopia.

Return on Equity was proved to have negative significant impact on deposit growth on Commercial banks. These results may imply that deposits are not substantially converted into loans, so larger growth rates of deposits can depress profitability implying having inactive or idle money. Thus, overall results show that bank profitability is inversely related to deposits. Therefore, it can be concluded that as Return on equity increase, growth in deposit decrease in Commercial banks of Ethiopia.

Limitations of Study

The study did not include qualitative information which should have been gathered by questioner and interview which give adequate data to explain the hidden issues that affect the relationship between deposits growth and other variables which are not shown here. An open-ended questionnaire, an interview or discussion would have given qualitative information to strengthen the results.

Data Availability and Reliability This study Conducted by using secondary data obtained from commercial banks, the National Bank of Ethiopia, and other institutions. Limited accessibility to complete, up-to-date, and reliable data may have affected the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the finding.

Geographical Scope. The research focuses only on selected commercial banks in Ethiopia, which may not fully represent the entire banking industry. Findings may not be generalizable to all banks or other financial institutions in the country.

Limited Variables Considered it might be worthy using a longer time series and more banks would have benefited different trends and results in addition, the study focuses on two internal and four external variables. Although several variables' determinants are analyzed (such as Technology and Innovation, branch accessibility, Trust and Confidence in Banks and service quality).

Exclusion of Informal Financial Systems. A significant portion of Ethiopia's population still relies on informal savings and credit associations (e.g., Equb and Idir). Since this study focuses only on formal banking institutions, these aspects are excluded.

Time Constraints. Due to time limitations, the study covers only a specific period, which may not capture long-term trends and structural changes affecting deposit mobilization.

Macroeconomic Instability. Ethiopia's economy is subject to inflation, currency depreciation, and political instability, which may distort the determinants of deposit mobilization during the study period.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested as possible solutions on the basis of the major findings and conclusions.

- Excess broad money supply will cause inflation and have a negative impact to the growth of the deposit of Commercial banks. The government should decrease its excess supply of broad money to the economy.
- Inflation will increase individual's inability to save since it influences the standard of living. Individuals tend to consume rather than saving their money. Therefore, government should device mechanism to control inflation such as reducing government expenditure and increasing tax on private business.
- The Ethiopian commercial banks have to give loan by considering their deposit and the risk of high loan to deposit ratio.
- The Ethiopian commercial banks have to work on creating of awareness about banking services by recruit sales persons, who have an experience in marketing, in order to advertise the products and services of the commercial banks through door-to-door activities.
- The Ethiopian commercial banks have to due diligence for the information gathered from the customer and the information given to the customer for the anti-money laundry and countering financial terrorism reports in order to minimize the threat created on the commercial bank's customers when the information's are gathered.
- For the branch operation managers, it's a serious implication that, branch operation managers of Ethiopian commercial banks should give consideration to number of branch and loan to deposit ratio when they set deposit mobilization techniques as they are found to be the most significant internal variables that affect commercial banks deposit. This will help them to make their deposit increased in the long run.
- The researcher recommend that the government should encourage investment with technology to take steps that ensures and address the high rates of unemployment which causes growth per capita GDP. It is found that economic growth is good for the growth of deposit in the banking sector.
- The Commercial banks need to convert deposit to loan to increase return on equity. If loan disbursement fails to increase the deposit will have negative impact keeping idle money to pay interest.
- The researcher observed that some of the banks have ratio more than 100% and that banks might not have enough liquidity to cover any unforeseen fund requirement and it may even affect capital adequacy and lead to asset liability miss-match Thus, the optimum goal of a bank can be achieved only with a balanced loan to Deposits ratio. The researcher recommends that commercial banks to keep loan to deposit ratio balanced as per the regulation.

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appendix
Deposit Growth

year	CBE	Awash	Dashen	CBO	united	NIB	Lion	BOA	verag e DPG
2015	75.8	30.09	28.83	42.55	45.49	33.46	87.51	29.23	42.45
2016	88.6	23.04	28	8.9	30.83	25.2	44.62	14.34	24.99
2017	64.33	26.82	16.73	-23.83	30.79	24.96	27.5	18.22	17.31
2018	82.99	18.86	18.78	-3.33	10.63	13.2	33.86	11.47	14.78
2019	64.75	36.3	12.7	31.68	20.26	14	21.26	25.47	23.10
2020	55.82	19.89	11.55	12.28	15.72	19.05	27.6	7.06	16.16
2021	45.39	23.13	12.06	22.98	24.26	23.35	65.89	22.22	27.70
2022	73.42	23.28	14.86	12.23	17.76	27.1	42.09	22.64	22.85
2023	83.11	33.98	22.08	26.55	26.59	32.14	38.54	51.82	33.10
2024	98.38	42.04	29.53	46.26	39.82	31.69	32.65	24.58	35.22

Consolidated from annual report data of banks

Loan to Deposit Ratio

year	CBE	Awash	Dashen	BOA	CBO	united	NIB	Lion	Average LDR
2015	77.83	51.67	54.9	54.4	28.7	61.7	64.3	66.1	46.77
2016	68.77	62.2	62.5	56.8	34.2	56.9	71.4	56.5	49.10
2017	63.89	54.7	65.6	66.2	64.1	84.4	66.2	64.1	57.01
2018	85.94	71.3	76.6	77.7	97	76.5	86.8	75	69.03
2019	51.85	65.6	78.1	88.4	104.8	96.8	97.5	95.3	76.87
2020	79.57	86.7	76.5	15.4	94.3	88.3	202.2	84	90.29
2021	83.62	95.2	86.6	83.6	87	97.8	109.2	91.3	81.01
2022	59.87	89.9	83.1	85.8	107	98	94	94.5	80.93
2023	98.43	95.2	93.4	92	109.4	101.1	96.3	89.7	83.59
2024	86.55	91	92.3	93.4	13.3	91.6	90.8	91.8	67.26

Consolidated from annual report data of banks

Return on Equity

Year	CBE	Awash	Dashen	BOA	CBO	United	NIB	Lion	Average ROE
2015	64.97	39.81	38.8	28	30.6	25.7	30.2	1.9	27.86
2016	81.73	36.6	40.8	33.5	30.2	38.8	31.1	20.5	33.07
2017	72.96	37.8	45.1	39.1	34.3	35.8	29.4	17.5	34.14
2018	80.33	32.1	48.9	31.8	28.6	36.9	25.5	23.7	32.50
2019	75.11	28.2	39.7	31.7	24.6	31.2	22.7	27.8	29.41
2020	98.46	31.9	36.9	23	14.3	22.9	21.1	20.3	24.34
2021	57.82	27	33	20.7	18.7	21.2	20.2	33.5	24.90
2022	86.74	25.06	28.31	22.94	17.1	20.7	18.2	32.7	23.57
2023	59.51	28.07	24.54	24.25	21.1	19.4	23.1	24.2	23.52
2024	64.73	30.24		18.04					

Consolidated from annual report data of banks

Summary of Data Collection from Annual Report

Year	Inflation Rate	Deposit Rate	Growth (PCGDP)	Broad money supply(m2)
2015	36.4	4.5	7.1	21
2016	2.8	4.5	7.5	26.6
2017	18.1	5.4	10.6	39.2
2018	34.1	5.4	32.2	30.3
2019	13.5	5.38	6.8	24.2
2020	8.1	5.38	14.4	26.5
2021	7.6	5.38	13.4	24.7
2022	9.7	5.38	9.5	19.9
2023	7.2	5.38	7.8	28.8
2024	13.1	8	0.9	29.2

Source: NBE Annual report